

VIDZEME REGION
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Vidzeme pilot members

Vidzeme Planning Region

Latvian Rural Forum

Institute of Agricultural Resources and Economics (AREI)

Baltic Open Solutions Center

People, Balance, Embedded

Results

Regional panel – consultative board involving broader (than usual) scope of stakeholders. Panel is being kept as a monitoring/consultation forum for strategic planning in the region

Foresight process / regional Action Plan development process - recognized as one of the best practices of stakeholder involvement in Latvia by a national think tank.

Foresight process as a capacity building intervention – almost all employees were involved in moderating interactive discussions with stakeholders. Provided high engagement, increased ownership over results.

New practical initiatives being currently developed (the Inclusion Week)

Newcomers recognized as a specific target group, will be highlighted in annual regional good practice awards as separate category. New cooperation with University of Agriculture on the theme developed, incl. new support from State Research program.

Lessons learned

Content related:

- Analysis of trends have proved very valuable and allowed stakeholders to apprehend the interconnectedness of local issues with global processes

Process related:

- Foresight takes time and continuous commitment by all involved
- The leading core has to have a good and realistic understanding on the process, potential gains (and losses)
- A broad toolbox and ability to use them properly is important to get attention, win credibility and stimulate serious discussions
- There are much more possibilities than limitations!

Contribution to LTV4RA

STRONGER: Empowered local communities & Social innovation

- Strengthening civic participation and public involvement
- Increasing the role of local communities in municipal and regional development planning, implementation and monitoring,
- strengthen citizens' links with municipalities and participatory budgeting, social innovation and knowledge platform creation,
- supportive environment and support mechanisms for citizen engagement and community initiatives

PROSPEROUS: Diversification of economic & Sustainable food production

- Strengthening rural SMEs for producing high-added value products and services
- Strengthening business cooperation, clusters and thematic networks,
- promoting networking of entrepreneurs and cooperation with research institutions,
- promoting the development of local products based on local resources,
- developing new types of business,
- promoting the involvement of young people in entrepreneurship.

**FOSTER COOPERATION AND
STRONG INSTITUTIONS**

**DEVELOPMENT AND GROWTH
THROUGH ADAPTING ECONOMIC
MODELS**

**IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF
LIFE IN THE REGION**

**PRESERVE AND WISELY
MANAGE NATURAL
SYSTEMS AND RESOURCES**

INNOVATION, SCIENCE AND
DEVELOPMENT
INDUSTRY
TRANSFORMATION

ACCESSIBLE EDUCATION
A SAFE, INCLUSIVE AND
HEALTHY SOCIETY
QUALITATIVE AND
AVAILABLE SERVICES

NATURAL CAPITAL

ADAPTATION TO
CLIMATE CHANGE

DIGITAL TRANSITION
COOPERATION AND
PARTICIPATION

CIRCULAR AND BIOECONOMY
EFFICIENT AND CLEAN
ENERGY

MOBILITY AND ACCESSIBILITY
IDENTITY AND STRONG
COMMUNITIES
SUSTAINABLE LIVING
ENVIRONMENT AND
HOUSING

NATURAL AND
CULTURAL HERITAGE

Action Plan adoption

Vidzeme Region Development Programme 2027 adopted by the Vidzeme Development council in April 2022

Municipal development programmes and Local Development strategies of Local Action Groups must mandatory align with the Vidzeme regional Development Programme

Stakeholders survey: programme is being used for development of other strategic documents > endorsement & use

Main users: strategic planners, project developers, researchers

Challenge: to become part of political agenda of municipal leaders

Case study

- Editing: No editing intended
- Translation: No
- Publishing: Ongoing discussion on possible publication with pilot partners
- Dissemination: Will be made available in the public communication together with other project resources and deliverables

Tools (guides)

The STEEPV Inventory of Drivers of Change: has played important role in development of the strategic framework of the Development Programme. Used also by municipalities and other stakeholders.

Guide to Deep Dives (Covid) & (Green Deal): – intended use during the next monitoring report of the DP

Guide to Deep Dives (CAP Reform): used by partners in the discussion process and proposals for MA

D1.8 Future Outlooks Methodology: has served as a guidance in RAP development

Ex ante/ex-durante methodology: (hopefully) provided a M&E framework that will be used

Tools (tech)

Regional SDM: currently is not usable. If revised may be very useful tool.

Semex: if operational will be used for various purposes. High interest from stakeholders.

Rural Attractiveness Explorer: do not see use as a tool yet, but when presented to stakeholders it served as a boost for the discussion for defining and searching for attractiveness in local level

Statistical Prediction tool: to create simple predictive models based on correlations and linear regression a tool was developed

Digital Innovation Hub: will be promoted and used as good repository

Atlas of Best Practices: used in different stakeholder seminars and meetings as inspiration and examples for representation of trends

Statistical Prediction tool

Shift 0 years

Life satisfaction

Shift 0 years

Input X and Predict Y ?

By selecting one of the previously created linear regression models we can predict the future values of the dependent statistical variable.

Please fill the date range to generate input fields to be filled for the independent variable. You can fill them manually or use a sketch area to draw a line describing the function.

Stored statistical model: ▾

From 2022

Till 2032

Variable

Location (optional): ▲